

CONSUMER ATTITUDE AND PURCHASE INTENTION TOWARDS INFLUENCE OF CELEBRITY ENDORSEMENT ON GENZs' FASHION CLOTHING

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ABSTRACT : *One of the widely utilized marketing strategies for influencing consumers' purchasing intentions is celebrity endorsement. Hence, the purpose of this study is to determine the influences on gen Z consumers' buying intentions in the city of Mysuru. This essay tries to provide a thorough analysis of the variables influencing consumers' decisions regarding clothes and textile products. Studies looking at variables influencing the marketing of textile goods, such as clothing and fashion items, were evaluated. Several cultural, societal, personal, psychological, and economic aspects are among these. ecological factors. Product qualities, purchasing channel, price, and marketing were included as market-related features.*

In order to ascertain their impact on the purchase intentions of gen Z consumers in the city of Mysuru, the dimensions or elements of attractiveness, credibility, congruence, and expertise were taken into consideration for this study. These factors were discovered through a review of the literature.

Keywords: *Personal, Psychological, Social, Pictorial, Cultural, Fashion, Market, Meaning, Mass customization, Physical, Purchase channel, Pricing, Promotion.*

INTRODUCTION

McCracken defines a celebrity endorser as “any individual who enjoys public recognition and who uses this recognition on behalf of a consumer good by appearing with it in an advertisement.” In advertising, celebrities have been used to promote goods and companies since the 18th century. Ever since it has grown into a popular advertising strategy and has been the focus of extensive study. Celebrity endorsements may be very advantageous for businesses, improving market share, sales, profits, and other metrics as well as brand awareness, recall, and familiarity. Celebrity endorsements have been increasingly popular in recent years all over the world, especially in light of the growth of digital marketing and the advent of social networking sites. According to statistical fluctuation, celebrities appear in about 25% of advertisements in Western nations, however, this percentage might reach 60% in East Asian nations. According to a study by the British research company Statista, 75% of respondents who work for advertising agencies say they utilize celebrities to advertise on social media. Additionally, according to Statista research, 98 percent of marketers think celebrities are very efficient in promoting companies and products on social media.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Nhu-Ty NGUYEN (2021) Regarding the OPPO F-series and singer Son Tung MTP in the Vietnamese context, the article aims to explain the impact of celebrity endorsers on customers' purchase intentions. It says that a brand's impact is thought to be the quickest and most efficient communication approach for creating an association and drawing in its target audience. The results indicate that brands, generally, and smartphone manufacturers specifically, should not only focus on these traits to choose an appropriate brand endorser but also need to anticipate some potential hazards when leveraging celebrity.

I Gusti Ayu Uthami Febriati and Ni Nyoman Rsi Respati (2020) This study seeks to investigate the impact of product quality and celebrity endorser reputation on consumer intention to purchase Emina cosmetics within Denpasar City. 100 respondents participated in this study, which used a purposive sample technique. Surveys were used to get the data. The path analysis method and the Sobel test are the data analysis techniques used. It demonstrates that brand image and purchase intention are positively and significantly impacted by the legitimacy of celebrity endorsers and product quality. The influence of celebrity endorsers' reputation and product quality on purchasing intention is moderated by brand image.

Yu Hua Cui and Yu-Ling Bai (2020) This paper aims to unveil the impact of Korean celebrity endorsement on the purchase intention of Chinese consumers, involving reliability and validity tests and a structural equation model. It concludes that celebrity endorsement positively affects purchase intention where celebrity expertise has the strongest impact.

Raksha R. Deshbhag and Bijuna C. Mohan (2020) The goal of this study is to see how celebrity credibility affects risk perception and purchasing intentions among Indian fast-moving consumer goods buyers. This study used a self-administered questionnaire with 18 measurement scales to survey 250 participants. The study's main findings show that celebrity trust and celebrity expertise are the most important dimensions of celebrity in influencing Indian FMCG consumers' risk perceptions. Consumers in India who buy FMCG products have a positive impact on their risk perceptions.

Kofi Osei-Frimpong, et al. (2019) This study explores the impact of celebrity endorsement and its moderating effect on negative publicity, involving 500 respondents. The findings reveal that a celebrity endorser with attributes like attractiveness, trustworthiness, and familiarity has a positive influence on consumers' perception of quality, purchase intentions, and brand loyalty. Hence celebrity endorsers' negative publicity had no moderation effect.

Zarith Delaila Abd Aziz, et al. (2019) In this study, Malaysian millennials' intentions to purchase local beauty and health goods are examined concerning the use of various celebrities as sponsors. The study could help marketers control marketing endeavors in their strategies by giving them a better knowledge of how celebrities may influence millennials' desire in using things.

Marium Mateen Khan, et al. (2019) This paper objectives to take a look at the impact of celebrity endorsement, perceived exceptional, and brand loyalty on client buying intentions. The findings imply that three aspects of celebrity endorsement—celebrity beauty, believability, and product match—promote consumers' intentions to make a purchase. Purchase intentions are also encouraged by brand loyalty and quality perception. Additionally, brand loyalty modulates the relationship between perceived quality and purchase intentions and influences perceived quality.

Karina Sokolova and Hajer Kef (2019) The persuasion cues associated with beauty and fashion influencers on YouTube and Instagram are investigated in this article. The authors focus more on the relationship between perceived credibility and purchase intent of the audience with the online influencer, and how those elements relate to physical and social attractiveness and attitude homophily. Physical attractiveness seems to have a negative or no association with PSI, however, attitude homophily has a favorable relationship with PSI. Purchase intent has large and favorable correlations of both influencer credibility and PSI.

Gina A. Tran, et al. (2019) This research examines a model of celebrity connectedness, celebrity attitude, celebrity-endorsed message receptivity, and celebrity-endorsed market offering purchase intentions. This Structural equation modeling was used to investigate the relationships. A total of 502 people responded to the survey. The results indicate that a person's level of attachment to their favorite celebrity is high. Both their receptivity to the celebrity-endorsed message and their receptivity to the celebrity-endorsed message are linked. Behaviors and attitudes in terms of application, the findings suggest that marketers should after careful consideration, select the best celebrity endorsers for advertisements.

Adil Adnan, et al. (2018) The research aims to investigate the effectiveness of celebrity as an advertising technique and to investigate the relationship between advertising technology and its purchase intentions buyer. The survey was conducted by 790 respondents. Different determinants of the celebrity endorsement model were checked by simple linear regression analysis based on consumers' purchase intentions. A relationship was found between celebrity nominations and purchase intentions buyers

through this study, and also identified both useful academic and administrative aspects of local and global brand advertisers.

Jasmina Ilicic, et al. (2018) Advertisers can use the Duchenne smile as a straightforward, positive facial cue to increase the genuine persuasive appeal of an endorser, whose status has declined in this study. The authors examined how customer attitudes toward commercials, purchase intent, and consumer perceptions of celebrity sincerity were influenced by celebrity attitude. Additionally, they investigated whether one might change their perception of a celebrity to change their attitude toward commercials and purchase intentions. Exposure to a celebrity sporting a Duchenne smile dramatically improves consumer views of a celebrity's sincerity when they have an unfavorable attitude about that celebrity.

Huai-Liang Liang and Ping-I Lin, (2018) Businesses must select the best endorser-product match to make the most of the limited endorsement budget available. Athlete endorsers have a bigger influence on customer views toward sports products than celebrity endorsers, according to prior studies. On the other hand, different endorsers may have differing levels of product influence. This essay's goal is to address these issues. The results showed that whereas athlete endorser-product fit increased customers' purchase intentions in low product involvement settings, celebrity endorser-product fit had no discernible moderating influence on buy intention. In high product participative circumstances, there was a moderating relationship between endorser-product fit and customer purchase intention.

Adnan Anwar and Dr. Tariq Jalees (2017) The purpose of this study was to determine how believability, attractiveness, and congruency affected purchase intention. The study used a 150-person sample size and a purposive sampling strategy. According to the study, congruency, credibility, and attractiveness were the best predictors of purchase intent.

Chin Vi Vien, et al. (2017) This study looked at the effects of Endorser Credibility, Endorser Likeability, Brand Image, and Brand Credibility on Brand Attitude and Purchasing Intention. In numerous linear regression studies, it was discovered that Brand Credibility positively influenced Brand Attitude more so than Endorser Credibility. The findings offer marketing guidance and support earlier studies on the significance of celebrity endorsement. More study is needed, particularly on how celebrity endorsement affects purchase intentions more so than brand trustworthiness.

Felix Martin and Fu Tao-Peng (2017) As a wellspring of attitudes and actions, identification has usually been linked to Western cultures rather than Confucian ones. Two empirical research examine how customers identify with celebrity ethical attributes to determine the impact of fame on purchase intent among Chinese consumers. For two investigations, online snowball sampling was employed to gather survey data. This study adds to the body of knowledge on morality among Chinese consumers and, more generally, on perceived moral authority. It is also one of the first studies to examine the moral consumption patterns of online gamers.

Karla McCormick (2016) The goal of the study was to determine whether the presence of a compatible product-endorser match influenced millennial consumers' purchase intentions and worked in the advertisement's favor. The celebrity endorsements used in this study were chosen after a pre-test. When it comes to selecting celebrity endorsers, previous studies have used a variety of methods; as a result, this study used one of them. The sample for this study was students between the ages of 20 and 29, who make up the generational cohort known as millennials. This age group is known as the millennial generation, while students under the age of 20 are known as generation Z. Millennials rated an unfamiliar celebrity endorsement positively, even though they had no intention of purchasing the product endorsed by the unfamiliar celebrity.

Mehrukh Salman and Uswa Naeem (2015) This study was carried out to assess the influence of ethnocentrism, brand attitudes, and celebrity endorsement on beverage purchase intentions in Pakistan. Data were gathered by a quantitative survey, and a route analysis using a total of 150 respondents was used to test the model. It was discovered that celebrity endorsements, brand attitudes, and ethnocentrism all significantly affect consumers' willingness to buy local brands.

Dr. Ruchi Gupta, et al. (2015) The current study aims to determine the impact of celebrity endorsements on consumers' purchase intentions through a survey of 336 Indian respondents who have been exposed to celebrity endorsements for various products/brands. The study also tries to figure out how these dimensions affect consumers' purchase intentions on an individual basis. The factor structure was reconfirmed using exploratory factor analysis. The impact of celebrity endorsements on purchase intentions was studied using structural equation modeling. Consumer purchase intent is significantly influenced by celebrity endorsements, according to the findings. The beta coefficients, on the other hand, show that celebrity endorsements have a low correlation with purchase intent. Furthermore, attractiveness and trustworthiness were discovered to have a significant impact on purchase intent, whereas expertise had no effect.

Hyojin Kim, et al. (2015) The authors of this study look into the factors that sway Para social relationships between SNS users and celebrities, as well as their impact on users' purchase intentions. The study found a link between social media use and celebrity para-social relationships. Over one week, they introduced the 12 celebrities to 40 men and women in their twenties and thirties. A total of 533 surveys were collected and analyzed as a result of the data collection. The results imply that new media, especially social networking sites, promote para-social interactions and that para-social ties and celebrity reputations affect SNS users' purchase decisions. The study found that new media boosts consumer demands and that celebrities have more influence over consumers' purchasing decisions in the new social media ecosystem.

Aysegul ERMEC SERTOGLU, et al. (2014) The goal of this study is to see if source credibility influences purchasing intent and to compare the perceived credibility of a created spokesperson versus a celebrity endorser, involving factors such as attractiveness, trustworthiness, and expertise on the purchase intention. A total of 326 young consumers were chosen for the study. The result shows that all three credibility dimensions have a positive relationship with purchase intention and that the created spokesperson is thought to be more trustworthy and competent, while the celebrity endorser is thought to be more attractive.

Eugenia Tzoumaka, et al. (2014) In this study, it is examined how endorser credibility traits like knowledge and trustworthiness, and also consumer traits like gender and team affiliation, affect the effectiveness of endorsements as indicated in purchase intentions. Gender differences were discovered in terms of team identification, not in terms of endorsers' perceived traits or efficacy. Differences in team identity significantly affected purchasing intentions but just slightly affected the trustworthiness of athletes. Among the two components of credibility examined, trustworthiness is a key differentiator for purchase intentions. Numerous theoretical and practical ramifications of the study are present.

Syed Rameez ul Hassan, R. A. J. (2014) stated that the study's primary focus is on endorsement, using Pakistani and Indian celebrities' traits to attest to their influence on consumers' intentions to buy existing products. They compared how endorsements from Indian and Pakistani celebrities affected the buying of those respective personalities. In Pakistan, a sample of 300 people was used to compare the effects of celebrity endorsement on purchasing behavior in India and Pakistan. Brands that are similar and competitive are chosen, with Pakistani and Indian celebrities endorsing them separately. They found that local and Indian celebrities who have a similar and negligible influence on the purchase image and brand loyalty are key factors of purchase intention.

RESEARCH GAP

Various researchers have published their papers on the various factors affecting Buying Behaviour but complete coverage of all the factors including in one paper is not possible. When we see the notable publisher's papers, they have concentrated on factors such as Attractiveness, Credibility, and Expertise affecting the customer's buying behavior as a whole. No similar research was conducted in Mysuru city on this particular topic.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Celebrities generally cost more or less depending on how huge or small the brand/product is. Understanding the scope of their credibility and how the association would affect the brand/product may make businesses more cost-effective, but more research is required to determine whether they have a higher or lower impact on consumers' buy intentions.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

The topic of the study is "Influence of Celebrity Endorsement on Gen Z s' Purchase Intention towards Fashion clothing" with special reference to Mysuru. It gives insight or more understanding to the marketers on the importance of the Who, Why, How, Where, and When's as well as on various aspects of the Celebrity endorsement, to attract customers, as well as use it as one of the strategies to compete against the rivals in the market.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the various dimensions of celebrity endorsement in the purchase intention of Gen Z customers' Fashion clothing.
2. To investigate the relationship between select dimensions of celebrity endorsement (Attractiveness, Credibility, Congruency, Expertise) with Gen Z Customers' purchase intention of Fashion clothing.
3. To measure the impact of the select dimensions of celebrity endorsement on Gen Z customers' purchase intention of Fashion clothing.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

On many levels, this study extends the field of research. First, it advances a theoretical understanding of the influence of celebrity endorsements on purchase intention. The study provides insights for marketers on effective marketing attribution spending on celebrity-sponsored advertising. In addition, it provides context-specific knowledge

regarding endorsements of celebrities and young people (Generations Z) Purchase intention of consumers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- The research design used in this study is descriptive.
- A non-probability sampling approach called convenience sampling was used to gather data from the respondents.
- A survey questionnaire was sent to people of generation Z (those born between 1997 - 2012) to gather primary data.
- Secondary data was collected via the internet/open sources, websites, and Standardized Questionnaires.
- Mysore localities were considered to be the target population for the survey.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

Hypothesis 1 –Celebrity attractiveness has a significantly positive influence on the intention to purchase fashion goods advertised by celebrities.”

Hypothesis 2 –Celebrity credibility has a significantly positive influence on the intention to purchase fashion goods advertised by celebrities.”

Hypothesis 3 –Celebrity congruency has a significantly positive influence on the intention to purchase fashion goods advertised by celebrities.”

Hypothesis 4 –Celebrity expertise has a significantly positive influence on the intention to purchase fashion goods advertised by celebrities.”

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The results of this study cannot be applied to consumers in other generations because it only included a sample of generation Z consumers.
- Focused specifically on celebrity endorsement of fashion clothing.
- The results cannot be applied to celebrity endorsements of different products or services in different areas or nations.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

RELIABILITY STATISTICS

“Cronbach's Alpha”	No. of Items
.986	21

Interpretation

A reliability test was conducted to test the reliability of the scale that is used for the collection of data. Cronbach's Alpha index was calculated to measure the reliability of the questionnaire that was prepared. 21 items were used in this study and the overall reliability score is 0.986 which indicates that the variables are reliable for further study.

Reliability Statistics of the dependent and the independent variables

VARIABLES	CONSTRUCTS	CRONBACH S' ALPHA VALUE	MEAN	SD	NO.OF ITEMS
Dependent	Consumer purchase intention	0.951	3.08	1.26	5
Independent	Attractiveness	0.948	3.15	1.18	4
	Credibility	0.938	3.15	1.18	4
	Congruency	0.936	3.09	1.19	4
	Expertise	0.947	3.17	1.23	4

The correlation was calculated and the results are shown in the tabular form below to find the correlation between the Independent Variables and Consumer purchase intention.

CORRELATION MATRIX

	Attractiveness	Credibility	Congruency	Expertise	Purchase Intention
Attractiveness	-	-	-	-	-
Credibility	0.918*** < .001	-	-	-	-
Congruency	0.898*** <.001	0.920*** < .001	-	-	-
Expertise	0.897*** < .001	0.903*** < .001	0.928*** < .001-		
Purchase Intention	0.893*** <.001	0.892*** <.001	0.894*** <.001	0.899*** <.001	

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Interpretation

- From the above table, we can see that the correlation between Attractiveness and Purchase intention has a high positive correlation as it projects the value of $r=0.893$ and the p-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.01.
- The correlation between Credibility and Purchase intention also shows a high positive correlation as it depicts the value of $r=0.892$ and the p-value is 0.000 which is less than 0.01.

- The correlation between Congruency and Purchase intention shows a high positive correlation as the value of $r= 0.894$ and the $p=0.000$ which is less than 0.01.
- The correlation between Expertise and Purchase intention shows a high positive correlation as the value of $r= 0.899$ and $p=0.000$ which is less than 0.001.

To test H1 to H4, Regression analysis was used and the results are tabulated from tables no; 4.4 to 4.7

REGRESSION

Regression Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.926	0.858	0.855	1.91629

Interpretation

From the above table analysis, the R square score is 0.858 and the adjusted R square score is 0.855 these scores ascertain us that the variables which are used to identify the impact on Consumer purchase intention help us explain the 85.8% of the equation.

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4514.468	4	1128.617	307.344	.000b
	Residual	745.450	203	3.672		
	Total	5259.918	207			

- Dependent Variable: PI
- Predictors: (Constant), Exp, Attr, Cred, Cong

From the above table, it's noticeable that the regression model is significant since the value of $p < 0.05$

COEFFICIENTS

Model Coefficients – Purchase Intention						
Predictor	Estimate	SE	t	p		
Intercept	-0.397	0.3877	-1.02	0.307		
Attractiveness	0.235	0.0629	3.74	<.001		
Credibility	0.197	0.0863	2.29	0.023		
Congruence	0.201	0.0884	2.28	0.024		
Expertise	0.317	0.0803	3.95	<.001		

Interpretation

- From the above table analysis, the relation between Attractiveness and Purchase Intention is said to be significant as the p-value is < 0.05 where $p=0.001$ in terms of Attractiveness.
- The relationship between Credibility and Purchase Intention also shows a significant relationship as the p-value is < 0.05 where the value of $p=0.023$ in terms of Credibility.
- The relation between the Congruence and Purchase Intention shows there is significant relationship as the value of p is < 0.05 and the value projected is $p=0.024$ for Congruency.
- The relationship between Expertise and Purchase Intention shows there is significant relationship as the value of $p < 0.05$ and the value projected is $p=0.001$ for Expertise.
- The estimated regression equation of Purchase Intention on select independent variables of the study is given by Purchase Intention $p = - 0.397$

+ 0.235 (Attractiveness) + 0.197 (Credibility) + 0.201 (Congruency) + 0.317 (Expertise)

Table Shows the results of the Research Hypothesis

SL NO	Research Hypothesis	Results
H1	“Celebrity attractiveness has a significantly positive influence on the intention to purchase fashion goods advertised by celebrities.”	Accepted
H2	“Celebrity credibility has a significantly positive influence on the intention to purchase fashion goods advertised by celebrities.”	Accepted
H3	“Celebrity congruency has a significantly positive influence on the intention to purchase fashion goods advertised by celebrities.”	Accepted
H4	“Celebrity expertise has a significantly positive influence on the intention to purchase fashion goods advertised by celebrities.”	Accepted

FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND SUGGESTIONS

FINDINGS

a. Correlation Analysis

As per the research findings, it was observed that all the independent variables i.e., Attractiveness, Credibility, Congruency, and Expertise showed a high positive correlation as they pose the r-value of 0.893, 0.892, 0.894, and 0.899 respectively.

b. Regression Analysis

As per the research findings it can be observed that the relationship between all the variables i.e., Attractiveness, Credibility, Congruency, and Expertise with Consumer Purchase Intention is as significant as the value of $p < 0.05$.

CONCLUSION

- The purpose of this study was to get a deeper understanding of the significance of who, why, how, where, and when as well as numerous components of celebrity endorsement to draw consumers and use it as a strategy to outperform competitors in the market. Additionally, this will assist marketers in properly attributing the marketing budget spent on celebrity-sponsored advertising.
- From the results, it is clear that the independent variable, such as attractiveness, credibility, congruency, and expertise, is very important to generation Z's decision-making process. Therefore, it is crucial to determine whether the chosen celebrity endorser matches these criteria and has the power to sway consumers' purchasing decisions.
- When it comes to demographic factors, we can see that females are more likely than males to respond to celebrity endorsements. Additionally, consumers with higher education and families with incomes in the moderate to the high range can make excellent targets.
- This study has some limitations because it only examined celebrity endorsement for fashion clothing i.e., the textile industry using a sample of 208 Gen Z respondents in the Mysuru area. Therefore, it would be difficult to generalize the findings to other celebrity endorsements of goods or services.

SUGGESTIONS

- My suggestion is to focus on independent variables like attractiveness, credibility, congruency, and expertise because research has shown that these qualities have a significant impact on gen Z's purchase intention.
- Marketers must pick a celebrity endorser who possesses several desirable traits, including a great personality, good or positive target group acceptance, and solid understanding and experience of the product, brand, or industry that they are advertising.
- Female consumers with higher education and family incomes in the moderate to the high range should be kept in mind as they are more likely to be influenced by celebrity endorsement and make the ideal target group.

REFERENCES

- Abdaziz, D. Z., Khalilomar, M., & Ariffin, S. (2019). The effects of celebrity endorsement towards purchase intention among students in one public university Malaysia. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Science*, 9(5), 498-507.
- Adil Adnan, Waqar Alam and Syed Asim Shah (2018). Determining the Impacts of Celebrity-Based Brand Endorsements on Consumers' Purchasing Intention.
- Anwarl, A., & Jalees, T. (2017). Celebrity endorsement and consumer purchase intentions. *Market forces*, 12(1).
- Deshbhag, R. R., & Mohan, B. C. (2020). Study on influential role of celebrity credibility on consumer risk perceptions. *Journal of Indian Business Research*.
- Febriati, I. G. A. U., & Respati, N. N. R. (2020). The effect of celebrity endorser credibility and product quality mediated by brand image on purchase intention. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research*, 3, 464-470.
- Gupta, R., Kishore, N., & Verma, D. P. S. (2015). IMPACT OF CELEBRITY ENDORSEMENTS ON CONSUMERS'PURCHASE INTENTION. *Australian Journal of Business and Management Research*, 5(3), 1-15.
- Ilicic, J., Kulczynski, A., & Baxter, S. M. (2018). How a smile can make a difference: Enhancing the persuasive appeal of celebrity endorsers: Boosting consumer perceptions of celebrity genuineness through the use of a "Duchenne Smile" in advertising. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 58(1), 51- 64.
- Jamil, R. A., & Rameez ul Hassan, S. (2014). Influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer purchase intention for existing products: a comparative study. Syed Rameez ul Hassan, RAJ (2014). Influence of celebrity endorsement on consumer purchase intention for existing products: a comparative study. *Journal of Management Info*, 4(1), 1-23.
- Khan, M. M., Memon, Z., & Kumar, S. (2019). Celebrity endorsement and purchase intentions: The role of perceived quality and brand loyalty. *Market forces*, 14(2).
- Kim, H., Ko, E., & Kim, J. (2015). SNS users' para-social relationships with celebrities: social media effects on purchase intentions. *Journal of Global Scholars of Marketing Science*, 25(3), 279-294.
- Liang, H. L., & Lin, P. I. (2018). Influence of multiple endorser-product patterns on purchase intention: An interpretation of elaboration likelihood model. *International Journal of Sports Marketing and Sponsorship*.
- Martin, F., & Tao-Peng, F. (2017). Morality matters? Consumer identification with celebrity endorsers in China. *Asian Business & Management*, 16(4), 272- 289.
- McCormick, K. (2016). Celebrity endorsements: Influence of a product- endorser match on Millennials attitudes and purchase intentions. *Journal of retailing and consumer services*, 32, 39-45.
- NGUYEN, N. T. (2021). The influence of celebrity endorsement on young Vietnamese consumers' purchasing intention. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(1), 951-960.
- Osei-Frimpong, K., Donkor, G., & Owusu-Frimpong, N. (2019). The impact of celebrity endorsement on consumer purchase intention: An emerging market perspective. *Journal of marketing theory and practice*, 27(1), 103-121.
- Salman, M., & Naeem, U. (2015). The impact of consumer ethnocentrism on purchase intentions: local versus foreign brands.

- Sertoglu, A. E., Catli, O., & Korkmaz, S. (2014). Examining the effect of endorser credibility on the consumers' buying intentions: an empirical study in Turkey. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 4(1), 66-77.
- Sokolova, K., & Kefi, H. (2020). Instagram and YouTube bloggers promote it, why should I buy? How credibility and parasocial interaction influence purchase intentions. *Journal of retailing and consumer services*, 53, 101742.
- Tran, G. A., Yazdanparast, A., & Strutton, D. (2019). Investigating the marketing impact of consumers' connectedness to celebrity endorsers. *Psychology & Marketing*, 36(10), 923-935.
- Tzoumaka, E., Tsiotsou, R. H., & Siomkos, G. (2016). Delineating the role of endorser's perceived qualities and consumer characteristics on celebrity endorsement effectiveness. *Journal of Marketing Communications*, 22(3), 307-326.
- Vien, C. V., Yun, C. T., & Fai, P. L. (2017). The effect of celebrity endorsement on brand attitude and purchase intention. *Journal of Global Business and Social Entrepreneurship (GBSE)*, 1(4), 141-150.
- Yu, H. C., & Yu, L. B. (2020). Influence of Korean celebrity endorsement on Chinese consumers' purchase intention towards fashion goods. *Journal of Fashion Business*, 24(6), 148-158.
- Information about the Textile Industry in India was referred from IBEF: <https://www.ibef.org/industry/textiles>
- Definition of a celebrity endorser was taken from <https://www.acrwebsite.org/volumes/7186#:~:text=Because%20a%20celebrity%20endorser%20is,product%20associations%20are%20easily%20recalled>